

VOLUME-2

ISSUE № 3 2024

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL JOURNAL

ISSN: 2181-4279

INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION RESEARCH

RESEARCH-EDU.COM

RESEARCH
ACADEMY

3/2024

INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION RESEARCH

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL JOURNAL

XALQARO TA'LIM TADQIQOTLARI

ILMIY-NAZARIY JURNAL

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

НАУЧНО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

Founder:
LLC "Academy of Educational
Research"

Scientific-theoretical journal
3/2024

**INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION
RESEARCH**

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The journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 20, 2023 as a mass media under the № 059 413

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physical education and sports, Tashkent, ChirchikE-mail: egamovduryod4@gmail.com**ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPING THE QUALITIES OF QUICKNESS AND AGILITY IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES**DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14225346>

Annotation. This article describes the development of physical qualities through innovative technologies and its effectiveness. Questionnaires about the innovative device LD TEST in the development of the quality of speed and agility of elementary school students. It has been written about the level of extracurricular clubs and physical education classes today.

Kalit so'zlar: physical qualities, sport, physical development, innovative, technology, LD TEST, speed, agility, sports centers, school, students, device.

Introduction.

In today's world, scientific research is being conducted across various fields, including physical education and sports, utilizing innovative devices that are widely used and rapidly spreading. These devices are aimed at enhancing the physical attributes of elementary school students by developing their skills, expanding their movement potential, and effectively nurturing fundamental physical qualities. The focus is on achieving psycho-physiological activation and improvement, addressing physical development aspects designed to promote such enhancements. In this regard, it is necessary to search for new innovative tools and forms to increase physical activity in children, which should be considered a social demand by the community.

In today's world, the increasing insufficiency in physical activity among students and the associated rise in related health issues have underscored the importance of addressing this through the enhancement of physical education programs. The goal is to cultivate a healthy and resilient generation that is equipped to combat these challenges, by fulfilling essential requirements to strengthen health and improve levels of mental development. These issues play a critical role not only in developing students'

physical attributes but also in enhancing their physical preparedness and increasing the effectiveness of extracurricular physical education activities. Recognizing this, it is crucial to devise new innovative mechanisms with instrumental methodological foundations to elevate the efficiency of students' physical fitness. This can be achieved by integrating a variety of movements and specialized physical exercises into the lesson process and actively involving students in extracurricular activities.

The aim of the research is to develop and scientifically substantiate a mechanism for enhancing the agility and quickness of primary school students through the use of innovative technologies.

Research tasks.

analyzing scientific and methodological literature related to the topic.;

determining the level of physical development and physical preparedness of primary school students;

the positive impact of applying innovative technologies aimed at developing quickness and agility in primary school students during extracurricular activities can be identified through surveys..

Research methods: The research involved the analysis of scientific-methodological literature, pedagogical experimentation, and the application of

mathematical statistical methods.

Organization of research: Experience Tashkent region, Chirchik city, IDUM No. 15. Questionnaires were received from physical education teachers of general secondary education school No. 5 of Samarkand region, Toyloq district, general education school No. 42 of Fergana region, Rishton district, and coaches of all Olympic and Paralympic sports training centers in our Republic.

The analysis of scientific and methodical work on the existing problem showed that scientific researches were not carried out sufficiently in order to determine the physical condition of students in secondary schools of our country.

Fundamental revision of the educational system and content in general education schools in accordance with the priority tasks set by the state to solve global issues related to the health of the growing generation, pedagogical science and remains the most important task of education.

The World Health Organization has recognized hypodynamia as a socially disadvantageous factor that affects the health of the growing generation. Through the method of pedagogical testing of children's physical condition, their movement abilities, it was possible to determine the factor of hypodynamia, which has a tradition of later progress in 17% of students.

Physical fitness of students of general education schools is the most important pedagogical problem - improving physical abilities of students and strengthening their health. Analytical review of the literature made it possible to conclude that the purpose of the physical education lesson at school is to improve the health of young students., this is the idea, V.S.Lednev; M.F.Agashin; E.A.Seytxalilov; T.S.Usmanxodjaev; F.A.Kerimov; A.A.Belkinim; R.S.Salamov; O.V.Goncharova; A.A.Abdullaev; Sh.I.Allamuratov; K.B.Muxammadiyev., Sh.X.Xankeldiev It has also been confirmed

in the scientific works of a number of scientists and practitioners in the field of physical education.

Research results and its discussion. In particular, the health of students is caused by many factors at school, such as: the increase in various colds, missing classes due to illness, body, visual impairment, the disproportion of the teacher's work to the students' abilities, non-observance of hygienic factors in the organization of educational processes, parents' lack of attention to children's health, students' lack of knowledge about a healthy lifestyle.

For this reason, it is necessary to pay great attention to the health of students at the primary school level. In particular, effective use of extracurricular time is the best way to achieve the desired results. In order to study and eliminate these problems, Tashkent Region, Chirchik City, No. 2 and No. 15, Samarkand Region, Toyloq District, No. 1 and No. 5, Fergana Region, Rishton Uman, No. 2 and 42 primary school teachers (24) and coaches of all Olympic and Paralympic sports training centers in our Republic (150) Case studies were conducted through questionnaires and anonymous questions.

In the questions of the questionnaire, information was obtained about the general health of primary school students, their interest in physical education classes, the role of sports in a child's life, the effective use of free time by students, and the Scandinavian style of walking. and analyzed.

In order to solve the tasks set in the dissertation, a pedagogical survey was conducted among 24 physical education teachers working in the above-mentioned schools.

The purpose of this questionnaire is to improve the process of extracurricular activities and classes in physical education, to raise the young generation to be physically fit, to introduce new innovative methods of education and services as the main instrument for developing educational programs. consists in reforming

organizational measures aimed at eliminating shortcomings.

This questionnaire is aimed at solving needs using the pedagogical method, in which a questionnaire-survey was conducted among physical education teachers on 7 questions.

According to the results of the questionnaire, all the respondents are specialists with higher education in the field of physical education, pedagogues in the educational system of this direction.

Question 1. Analyzing the state of the material and technical base of general education schools for conducting basic training on physical education and organizing physical education wellness activities with students? 67.4% showed that there are satisfactory conditions for conducting physical education classes and physical education sports events, 14.8% have relatively good and 26.7% have insufficient material sports base. This situation indicates that it is not possible to carry out basic training and physical education and health activities with young students at a methodologically high level.

Question 2. How confident are you in your knowledge of the most modern scientific and methodological approaches in the field of physical education? to our question, 18.6% (28 people) answered 90%; 41% (61 people) and 70%; 32% (48 people) answered 50% and 8.4% (13 people) answered 30%. The results of the answers to this question showed that 41% of the total 150 participants, i.e. (61 people), believed that 70% of their knowledge was the highest answer option.

Question 3. To the question "What difficulties do you face when conducting physical education classes in secondary schools?", 40.4% (60 people) answered that there is a lack of inventory, the gym does not meet the standard requirements, it is unsatisfactory; 41% (61 people) have sports equipment and equipment, but not enough; the inventory is sufficient, satisfactory, but the gym is not available, 5.1% (9 people) answered that the gym

meets the standard requirements, that the inventory is sufficient; 13.5% (20 people) gave an excellent answer. In order to ensure a scientific approach to the physical education system in this question of the survey, it will be important to provide more detailed information about the specific difficulties reported by the physical education teachers. This includes, for example, developing the nature of the challenges related to resources, equipment, curricula, student behavior or other factors affecting the effective delivery of physical education classes in secondary schools.

Question 4. How do you assess the level of physical fitness of students? to our question, 52.2% (78 people) of the total participants answered well; 34.3% (52 people) are satisfied; 6.2% (10 people) were dissatisfied and 7.3% (10 people) chose the excellent answer.

Question 5. "Is it possible to organize physical education classes at an interesting level for all students?" — to the question, 16.4% (25) of the participants answered by organizing lessons in an unconventional way; 32.9% (49 people) through national action games; 21.9% (33 people) answered that by using different methods and 28.8% (43 people) by using game and competition methods in lessons.

Question 6. To the question "Do you use new pedagogical technologies in physical education classes?", 27.5% (41 people) answered that we cannot use them, there are no conditions; 27% (40 people) use the answer that the conditions are sufficient; 38.7% (58 people) sometimes use it; 5.1% (8 people) answered that we organize at a high level, and 1.7% (3 people) answered that they do not know how to use new pedagogical technologies.

Question 7. "How important is the role of clubs in addition to physical education classes for the general well-being and academic activity of secondary schools?" 66.3% (100 people) answered the question - it is very important; 30.9% (46 people) are important; 0.56% (1 person) answered that

it is not important and 2.24% (3 people) answered that they did not know (see Figure 1).

According to the results of the anonymous survey, all the respondents are coaches with higher education in the field of physical education in training centers for Olympic and Paralympic sports:

Question 1. What do you think about the innovative device LD TEST? In 77.4%, I believe that technology that is convenient

for use in training is a necessary device that increases accuracy while reducing the human factor, 14.8% answered that I do not use innovative technologies, and 7.8% answered that I do not understand technical devices. This situation indicates that it is not possible to carry out basic training and physical education and health activities with young students at a methodologically high level.

Figure 1. Results of questionnaires received from specialists are displayed in percentages

Question 2. Does LD TEST have a positive effect on children and practitioners without an innovative device? 90.6% of the participants answered the question (yes); 9.4% (don't know) ; 0% (none) was found to be the highest response option.

Question 3. Do specialists face difficulties in using the LD TEST innovative device during training?" to our question, 80.1% (no) answered that there are no difficulties in using it, and 19.9% (yes) answered our questions because of lack of technological literacy.

Question 4. Would you use the LD TEST innovative device in your training? to our question, 83.7% answered that we would definitely improve the physical fitness of children and participants using this device,

16.3% answered our questions that they would use it if the organization provided us with this equipment. (See Figure 2)

In addition to physical education classes, each term of the academic year differs in terms of content. The differences lie in the specific features of using certain sports elements in the classroom. According to scientists in the field of physical education, the use of multi-dimensional development exercises during the physical education lesson reduces the time of basic exercises. There are both basic exercises and additional exercises that we offer to cover the physical activity of elementary school students.

The implementation of the physical education curriculum directly affects the

Figure 2. Diagram view of an anonymous survey of coaches of training centers for Olympic and Paralympic sports

development of the quality of each tool in primary school students. The body of elementary school students develops under the influence of activities outside physical education classes.

Summary.

The results of the research reveal several main problems facing the science of physical education in our Republic. For example, a large number of students indicate a low level of participation in physical education classes, many consider a lack of interest or motivation as the main obstacle to their participation. There are challenges related to a lack of resources and training for teachers to provide high-quality physical education, including limited access to sports equipment and facilities.

Based on these conclusions, it is clear that there is a need to significantly improve the scientific and methodological foundations of physical education in general education schools in our republic. It will develop a more comprehensive and evidence-based curriculum, provide additional resources and training for teachers, and engage parents and community members in promoting the importance of physical education classes for the overall health and well-being of students. involves engaging. Through a scientific and evidence-based approach to these issues, expert teachers and researchers together intend to improve the

system of extracurricular activities on physical education in our republic that will meet the needs of students.

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